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Initial Assessment of Developments and Revision of the Scientific Challenges - Optimising Magnetically Confined Plasmas with GENE

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the progress on the code GENE and GENE-X since the last deliverable, which was handed in end of June 2023. On our side, two persons are working on the project, a third person could not yet start due to bureaucratic hurdles. The main progress in this deliverable has been done on two tracks. First, the porting of the GENE-X code to GPU progressed significantly by now being able to run the full right-hand side computation on a GPU, although not yet performantly. The second achievement was a design and a first test implementation of a library for the block-structured grids (BSG) to leverage their usefulness also in GENE-X.

Additionally, we modified the Figure of Merit in a way to take into account progress in the development of the BSG library also in the FOM.

Work on the scalability improvement of the field solver has been postponed until more work power is available.

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1 Introduction

GENE and GENE-X are grid-based microturbulence simulation codes solving the gyrokinetic Vlasov-Maxwell system of integro-differential equations. Both codes work on a 5D physical grid consisting of three spatial coordinates and two velocity space coordinates, the velocity along the field lines v_{\parallel} and the magnetic moment μ . Whereas GENE uses a field aligned coordinate system with the spatial coordinates x (radial), y (binormal) and z (along the field line), GENE-X employs a fieldline-coordinate independent (FCI) approach. The latter uses the cylindrical coordinate system R , Z and ϕ .

Both codes have two main parts, first the computation of the right-hand side of the Vlasov equation, which mainly consists of stencil operations in different directions and the computation of the nonlinearity (which involves 1D FFTs in the case of GENE). The second important part is the solution of the field equations, which are linear equations solved in all poloidal planes independently. The input to these equations are the zeroth (density) and first (parallel current) moment of the distribution function, which are computed by an MPI_Allreduce operation over the velocity space processes.

In the deliverable D1.2, we have shown the current shortcomings of the two codes with respect to the target challenge. One big task is to port the GENE-X code to GPUs, for which we show the first steps in this deliverable. A second task has been the optimization of the fieldsolver scaling in the velocity space directions. There has been no progress, yet, due a lack of man power. The third point shown in D1.2 was the problem of strongly varying background temperature, which leads either to too many points or to an underresolution in velocity space. To overcome this problem, we started to work on a library to implement the block-structured grid approach and to make it available for all codes of the GENE family.

2 Revision of the Scientific Challenge

The Scientific Challenge has not changed. We still head for an ab-initio prediction of density and temperature profiles in the ITER tokamak using the three codes: GENE for the core, TANGO for the transport evolution and GENE-X for the edge to the wall part.

The Figure of Merit for this simulation was given as

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{\text{Time per time step} \times \text{total stream BW}}{\text{FP size} \times \text{total number of grid points}}$$

This FOM will not improve if we employ an algorithm that uses fewer points, but gives correct results of the same accuracy. This is the case for the "Block-structured grids" that are on our roadmap. To account for the improvements with this algorithm, we suggest to change the FOM to the following:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{\text{Time per time step} \times \text{total stream BW}}{\text{FP size} \times \text{total number of grid points full}}$$

where the "total number of grid points full" stand for the number of grid points that would be necessary without algorithmic changes.

It should be made clear that this change does only affect algorithmic changes that reduces the number of needed grid points, it does not change the target of a FOM below 6000 as defined in the proposal.

3 Summary of developments

3.1 GPU development

For GENE-X, the GPU port was pursued and led finally to a functional code that is able to run the right-hand-side computation on the GPU. The GPU code is not yet optimized and hence the performance is suboptimal and far from the target case.

GENE-X features Fortran/C++ interoperability specifically for GPU acceleration on the auxiliary C++ layer for better GPU support. A directive-based approach employing OpenACC or OpenMP offload has been chosen for GENE-X. The reason for this is the fact that in the pure CPU code OpenMP directives were well suited for shared memory parallelization in our software design. Another motivation for the use of a directive-based approach is that GENE-X is currently under heavy development with respect to the physics model and directives are generally easier to maintain, to adapt and to extend compared to low-level implementations, such as CUDA or HIP. However, the multigrid-based field solver in GENE-X, which is being developed in the separate PARALLAX library, is ported to GPU by using CUDA directly. The solver is not affected by the physics extensions of the main code and is therefore a nearly static piece of code.

Explicit memory management is preferred in GENE-X to have a better control of the latency of data transfers between CPU and GPU. In GENE-X, dedicated data containers manage the memory copy between CPU and GPU. Higher-level data containers manage the halo communication between MPI processes and have been ported to C++. This enables us to leverage available GPU-aware MPI functionality that furthermore reduces the CPU-GPU latency. The functionality of direct GPU-GPU communications in GENE-X still requires further investigation of its robustness.

Currently, around 80% of the functionality of GENE-X is ported to GPUs, and the optimization process just started. Validity of the ported code has been checked carefully throughout the porting process with the help of continuous integration and many functional tests.

All changes can be reviewed in our development gitlab repository¹. It is not public, but access can be given on request for reviewing purposes. The publication of the code is planned to be done during the project, but is not yet implemented.

3.2 Block-structured grids

The target case for predicting density and temperature profiles for ITER has a well-known problem: Both codes GENE and GENE-X uses a velocity space grid for the two coordinates v_{\parallel} and μ . In our standard approach, the grids are fixed for all space coordinates. However, the background temperature varies strongly with the radius and can change by a factor of 100 from the core to the edge. To get a good velocity space resolution for all radial positions, the spacing of the grid points is given by the low-temperature side, whereas the extent of the grid is given by the high-temperature side. Fulfilling both constraints together leads to a very high number of velocity space grid points.

¹<https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/phoenix/genex>

The idea of the block-structured grids (BSG) is to subdivide the radial direction in a small number of blocks (3-5 equally sized blocks are usually enough) and change the extent of the velocity space grids in dependence of the background temperature, but keep the same number of grid points. With this approach, which has been first implemented in ref.[1, 2], we can reach a high resolution with a fixed number of grid points for the price of a more complicated implementation. We are working on a library encapsulating this approach and making it usable in all codes of the GENE family.

We plan to implement the BSG library, tentatively called Gblocks, in C++ while providing a suitable API for GENE and GENE-X in Fortran. Gblocks essentially encapsulates the stencil operations over the BSG supporting both CPU and GPU backends. Further, we plan to employ the gtensor library which supports operations for multi-dimensional arrays and is used to abstract the methods for different GPU architectures.

An important feature of the library design is to not disturb the structure of the codes, which requires us to work with the existing data structures and limit large memory allocations. To achieve this, the library currently is planned to provide three high level API functions with several low level API depending on the code requirements. These high level API provides objects that target the three main abstract classes: CreateBSG, SetArray and SetOperation. CreateBSG class will help setup the fundamental BSG framework for the required code. SetArray will use the CreateBSG object and map the existing data structures on to the grid. Finally, the operations object will work on the SetArray objects and perform the required operations.

As a first step, we have developed the basic structure of the library with a minimal implementation to understand and test the object interactions. This mainly concerns the planning of a robust software design allowing for an efficient inter linkage of the objects. In the next stage, we plan to link the library initially to GENE and test the high level API purely from an interface perspective. This involves carefully understanding how the existing arrays are interfaced with the library. Further, we will introduce an implementation and its accompanying tests for basic operations. After setting up a successful working model for an operation, we will expand this implementation to the full code. This framework will be further adapted to also support GENE-X.

3.3 Improvement of the scaling of the field solver

The problem has been defined and a first solution has been sketched but no detailed design or implementation occurred.

As the problem comes from the fact that the inputs to the field solver are moments that come from the reduction of the distribution function over the velocity space and are therefore redundant on these processes, a first idea is to parallelize the field solver over these processes.

In GENE, the field solver itself is a linear system of equations just for the radial points (around 1000 points) and is solved independently for all k_y modes and for all z positions. One possibility is to redistribute the k_y and z points to all processes in y, z, v_{\parallel} and μ direction and/or to parallelize the backsubstitution step of the LU decomposed radial linear solver over the velocity space processes. Both approaches, as well as a combination will be followed.

For GENE-X, currently the field equations are solved for each poloidal plane inde-

pendently. The solver is not parallelized with MPI, but uses OpenMP for parallelization and is therefore limited to one shared memory node per poloidal plane. The main reason for this limitation is that the field solver is inherently a 3D problem and is independent of the underlying representation of the particle physics. This was also the reason for keeping the field solver in a separate library which is then used by different physical representation of the particle physics, i.e. a gyrokinetic representation as in GENE-X or a fluid representation as in GRILLIX. To reuse the same field solver for both (or more) codes is simplified by a pure OpenMP implementation of this solver. For our purposes of the improvement of the scalability of the solver, we have to lift this limitation and have to parallelize the solver at least in a way to use the full node of an Exascale system. Currently, a multigrid preconditioner to a GMRES iterative solver is used. It has to be investigated which parallel iterative solver is best suited for the parallel solution of the field equations.

4 Revision of Gap analysis

The three subsections of the previous section also mark the main gaps that have to be closed by this project on the way to the target challenge. A new scaling analysis is not necessary as no work has been done on improving the scaling of the fieldsolver or the collisions. For the block-structured grid approach, we do not have a working implementation that is fully functional, so also there no new gap analysis would bring any new content.

The only point that changed since the last analysis is the GPU port of GENE-X. There we can do some of the runs again and compare the results. As mentioned in section 3.1, only the functionality has been ported to run on GPUs, but the kernels and the full implementation has not yet been optimized. So we do not find a performance gain, although it is a big step. Only with the functionality to run the full rhs of the Vlasov equation on the GPU, we have the possibility to profile, analyze and finally optimize our implementation.

The reduced case of the target case, which is described in detail in deliverable D1.2, has been run again to measure the performance with the newly implemented changes. The comparison can be seen in Fig. 1. In this figure we show the main code parts, i.e., the field equations (Maxwell and Ohm's law solver) dominate, followed by the static operators of the Vlasov equation (mainly stencil operations). Further, the collisions take some amount of runtime, whereas the exchange ('ex') is not relevant on this parallelization scale. The colors stand for the reference case from D1.2 (blue), the current Fortran implementation run on the CPU (orange) and a GPU implementation with OpenMP Target directives (green). For the GPU run we were using one GPU per MPI rank, hence 4 GPUs per node, in total 80 A100 GPUs.

As a usual first step in porting a CPU code to GPU, we do not see a performance gain, but the important point is that the main functionality of the code is now able to use the GPU. There is now a lot of potential for optimization on the data handling, on the individual kernels, on the libraries used and so on.

The big gain that can be seen for the pure CPU code comes from the different parallelization distributions used. In the D1.2 runs we used 20 Raven nodes with 20 MPI

Figure 1: Comparison of the reduced target case from D1.2 on 20 Raven nodes with the current code. The different blocks stand for different parts of the code. All executable have been created with GNU compiler 11, but the distribution for the blue run was one rank per node (72 threads), whereas for the other two runs we used 4 ranks per node (18 threads).

processes (so one MPI process per node) and 72 OpenMP threads per MPI process. This was motivated by the fact that we would need this kind of distribution for the Exascale runs in order to be able to use all available cores. In the runs reported here, we want to make use of all GPUs per node (4 A100 per node) and for this we have to use 4 MPI processes per node and 18 OpenMP threads per process. As expected, the OpenMP scaling is quite bad in the code from D1.2 and did not change much for the current code. It must be mentioned that this behaviour is compiler dependent and the results are done with the gnu compiler, version 11. Using a recent Intel compiler, we measure a substantially improved run time. The main point here is to compare the GPU implementation with the CPU code and for this the distribution has to be adapted. During the project, we want to develop the code in a way, that we are able to use all node-local GPUs from one MPI process. In Table 1 the measured times are listed for reference.

	total	Maxwell	static	Ohm	coll	dyn	ex
CPU D1.2	96.4	46.5	39.7	5.7	10.0	0.3	2.0
GPU current	35.1	26.2	1.0	6.2	3.2	0.9	0.2

Table 1: Runtime per timestep in seconds for the different code parts. Compared are the results from deliverable D1.2 and the GPU port of the current code version.

5 Revision of Roadmap

The roadmap defined in the last deliverable has not changed. We will further work on the GPU porting of GENE-X. In addition, the improvement of the scalability of the field solver in GENE and GENE-X with the velocity space processes is an important point.

Also the development of the library for the block-structured grids is ongoing and the proposed change of the FOM (see Sec. 2) will also account for it in the improvement of the FOM.

6 Conclusion

In this deliverable we reported the progress on the two codes GENE and GENE-X. While the first code (GENE) has not undergone a larger improvement, just some tidy-up for setting up a new release version, the latter (GENE-X) got a substantial upgrade. The effort to port it to the GPU has done a big leap in porting the full functionality to the GPUs. As usual in this kind of porting effort, the performance is not yet better than on the optimized CPU case, but nonetheless this is an important intermediate step. Compared to the performance results of the reduced case in deliverable D1.2 on 20 Raven nodes we get an improvement of a factor 3 for the pure CPU version due to some optimizations and the same performance for the GPU runs with usage of OpenMP target directives for GPU execution.

As a second point, we reported on the design of a library for the inclusion of block-structured grids in both codes. For this library a first design has been done and also the implementations started.

The third point of our roadmap, the improvement of the scalability of the field solver of both codes, has been postponed due to lacking manpower.

These results are promising and we can keep our roadmap for the project as described in D1.2.

References

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